

DEVELOPMENT OF A MOBILE APPLICATION THAT PROVIDES INFORMATION ABOUT THE ACTIVITIES OF SMALL BUSINESSES

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Annotation: *In this article, there is information about development of a mobile application that provides information about the activities of small businesses. In addition, it provides some types of mobile application.*

Key words: *a mobile application, small business, tools, platforms, services.*

The mobile application is a multifunctional tool for quick access at a convenient time for the user to your goods and services. Exists a huge number of universal tools for developing mobile applications on popular IOS and Android platforms. Each of them has its advantages and disadvantages. Knowing all the positives and negatives platforms, you can use the resources of the gadget more rationally, save energy and achieve maximum performance.

IOS is a mobile operating system for smartphones, electronic tablets, wearable players and some other devices developed and manufactured by the American company Apple. IOS is closed and rather conservative system, as well as on it paid software is installed, which is characterized as a minus of this operating system [1]. A more detailed description of the parameters gives the ability to weigh all the pros and cons of the IOS operating system.

Android

Android is an operating system for smartphones, communicators, tablet computers and digital players. Core based Linux and Google's own implementation of the Java Virtual Machine.

Originally developed by Android, Inc., which was then bought by Google. Subsequently, Google initiated the creation of the Open Handset Alliance. Alliance (OHA), which is currently engaged in support and further platform development [2]. Android allows you to create Java applications, controlling the device through libraries developed by Google. Android Native Development Kit allows you to port libraries and components applications written in C and other languages.

As mentioned earlier, there are many ways develop a decent mobile application. Distinguish set mobile platforms that will help you create an

application within a budget and fast. Let us look at some of the most popular platforms to create mobile applications.

Appery.io

Appery is a cloud service for creating mobile applications on Android, iOS and Windows Phone, including open-source Apache Cordova framework (Phone Gap) with access to built-in components.

Getting started in the presented cloud service is quite simple, since nothing needs to be installed and downloaded. Visual editor with using drag and drop components builds a user interface.

You can also connect to any REST API and instantly add cloud database and link it to the application, if you need data, you can save. The plugin directory has all the necessary functionality, to create your own plugins. This development method is quite in demand, as there is a free trial version for 14 days.

Mobile roadie

Mobile Roadie is an app builder for iOS operating systems and Android. This platform supports all media formats, automatically importing RSS, Twitter or keywords from Google News and updating real time custom chat. Features of the free Mobile Roadie Connect service show a preview of the application as it will be seen by users.

The service checks the quality and appropriateness of the application content. In Mobile Roadie content can be transferred directly to the application, the API does not depend on language, so that data transmission is carried out in different formats, including XML, JSON, PHP, CSV and HTML. Can easily create unique look applications, apply it on all platforms and use marketing tools after launch. Cost of this service: \$125 per month (Core version) and \$667 per month (Pro version).

TheAppBuilder

TheAppBuilder is a software that is suitable for employees, customers, events and advertising media using two approach, that is, the service offers tools for service applications and programs.

Using a special library AppLibrary, users have access to a window with numerous applications, which can be designed in the style of the chosen brand. There is an opportunity to protect public and private applications with passwords, sending them through virtual store and creating conditions for directory integration TheAppBuilder's Active Directory and existing users [3].

In the presented cloud service, updating the structure and content applications are quite easy to make even after launch, because you can make an

infinite number of changes and apply them on mobile platforms in one click. The platform supports iPhone, iPad and Android, and the update takes effect one minute after confirmation [4]. Price the policy is presented upon request, and there is also a trial version on the server.

The software industry delivers to the market daily a large number of new software products, or various modifications of versions of already existing software.

Business software is all kinds of services and programs through which the company that uses them extracts profit.

To meet the same information needs the user is offered, as a rule, several dozen software products. This is especially evident when solving the problem of choosing or other software product for a new information system. One of the aspects of the problem of choice is the consideration of the prospects for the development of the chosen software, which are largely determined by common software development trends. In turn, knowledge development trends in the field of software allows the user it is more reasonable to choose one or another application or system [5].

Creation of software for personal computers some ten years has turned from the occupation of lone programmers into important and powerful industry. Therefore, the development of software software intended for a wide range of users is no longer in the competition of individual programmers, but in the process fierce competition between manufacturers software. Share of non-commercial software constantly declining and increasingly limited to programs created in the process of scientific research or for your own pleasure.

Considering the trends of intensive development of the software market software, it is safe to say that the development of mobile applications claims a great future, since today this segment is the subject of a very broad discussion. Today phones and electronic tablets have become an integral part of everyday life.

Consequently, a variety of applications and add-ons to them are becoming more and more in demand for both leisure and business. Outside whether we are chatting with friends or looking for any information in the global network, without the corresponding software is no longer needed.

The development of mobile applications deserves special attention. Analytical software products, control systems and control, as well as a wide variety of digital communications have become an essential attribute of any modern company.

The optimal solution for business is to create a number of versions mobile programs that work with a large number of devices that are "friendly" with different operating systems. Software performance and creation intuitive clear and convenient user interface allows you to engage the largest possible number of users of "smart" phones and electronic tablets.

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